

Supplementary table 1 - Checklist for medication review

The overall medication treatment:

- Is the medication treatment in accordance with the patient's clinical status?
- Is the treatment of the patient's diagnosis following treatment guidelines?
- Are there diagnoses/conditions/diseases that are not being treated?
- Is the drug treatment unnecessarily complicated for the patient? Is the treatment feasible for the patient?

The specific medications:

- Is there an indication for treatment with the medication?
- Is the medication effective for the disease/disorder for which it is prescribed?
- Is the prescribed medication appropriate for the disease/disorder for which it is prescribed?
- Is the medication effective for the disease/disorder for which it is prescribed?
- Is the dose too low, correct, or too high?
- Is the dosage regimen appropriate?
- Is the patient compliant with the medication?
- Is there information that indicates that the patient is using the medicine on the wrong way?
- Are there unnecessary double medications?
- Is there information to suggest that the patient is experiencing side effects? Which medication can cause side effects?
- Does the medication treatment present a risk for medication interactions?
- Is the medication contraindicated? Are there special precautions that are important to be aware of?
- Is the medication the cheapest alternative compared to others with the same effect?

Supplementary table 2 - DRP Causes according to PCNE classification

[N.B. One problem can have more causes]

	Main category	Code	Sub-category
Prescribing & selection	1. Medication selection The cause of the (potential) DRP is related to the selection of the med. (by patient or health professional)	C1.1	Inappropriate med. according to guidelines/formulary
		C1.2	No indication for med.
		C1.3	Inappropriate combination of med., or med. and herbal remedies, or med. and dietary supplements
		C1.4	Inappropriate duplication of therapeutic group or active ingredient
		C1.5	No or incomplete med. treatment in spite of existing indication
C1.6		Too many different med./active ingredients prescribed for indication	
	2. Medication form The cause of the DRP is related to the selection of the med. form	C2.1	Inappropriate med. form/formulation (for this patient)
	3. Dose selection The cause of the DRP is related to the selection of the dose or dosage	C3.1	Med. dose too low
		C3.2	Med. dose of a single active ingredient too high
		C3.3	Dosage regimen not frequent enough
		C3.4	Dosage regimen too frequent
		C3.5	Dose timing instructions wrong, unclear or missing
	4. Treatment duration The cause of the DRP is related to the duration of treatment	C4.1	Duration of treatment too short
		C4.2	Duration of treatment too long
Disp	5. Dispensing The cause of the DRP is related to the logistics of the prescribing and dispensing process	C5.1	Prescribed med. not available
		C5.2	Necessary information not provided or incorrect advice provided
		C5.3	Wrong med., strength or dosage advised (OTC)
		C5.4	Wrong med. or strength dispensed
	6. Med. use process The cause of the DRP is related to the way the patient gets the drug administered <i>by a health professional or other carer</i> , despite proper dosage instructions (on label/list)	C6.1	Inappropriate timing of administration or dosing intervals by a health professional
		C6.2	Med. under-administered by a health professional
		C6.3	Med. over-administered by a health professional
		C6.4	Med. not administered at all by a health professional
		C6.5	Wrong med. administered by a health professional
		C6.6	Med. administered via wrong route by a health professional
Use	7. Patient related The cause of the DRP is related to the patient and his behaviour (intentional or non-intentional)	C7.1	Patient intentionally uses/takes less med. than prescribed or does not take the med. at all for whatever reason
		C7.2	Patient uses/takes more med. than prescribed
		C7.3	Patient abuses med. (unregulated overuse)
		C7.4	Patient decides to use unnecessary med
		C7.5	Patient takes food that interacts
		C7.6	Patient stores med. inappropriately
		C7.7	Inappropriate timing or dosing intervals
		C7.8	Patient unintentionally administers/uses the med. in a wrong way

		C7.9	Patient physically unable to use med./form as directed
		C7.10	Patient unable to understand instructions properly
Seamless	8. Patient transfer related The cause of the DRP can be related to the transfer of patients between primary, secondary and tertiary care, or transfer within one care institution.	C8.1	Medication reconciliation problem
	9. Other	C9.1	No or inappropriate outcome monitoring
		C9.2	Other cause; specify
		C9.3	No obvious cause

Distribution of DRP causes by subcategories in the study

